

CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES OF RISK FACTORS IN CHRONIC CEREBRAL ISCHEMIA.

Abdurasulova Nozima Abduvokhidovna

Department of neurology and medical psychology
of Tashkent Medical Academy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8313920>

Chronic brain ischemia (SMI) is a specific type of vascular brain pathology caused by gradual progressive diffuse disruption of the blood supply to the brain, as a result of which it is expressed by the development of various defects [4,5]. Stress and depression are a manifestation of SMI. Stress-(derived from English, meaning "stress" - voltage) is a protective reaction of an organism manifested by neuroendocrine and metabolic processes in response to exogenous and endogenous influences. The term was introduced into scientific medicine in 1936 by the Canadian scientist Hans Sele, who defined stress as "the nespecific response of the body to any demand imposed". During Stress, excitation of MNS (stem and limbic system), excitation of the hypothalamus (increased levels of corticoliberin tyreoliberin through the medial and posterior sympathetic compartments), increased levels of corticoliberins in the blood affect stimulation of the adenoggipophysis compartment of the pituitary, leading to increased production of AKTG. This affects the scaly part of the adrenal gland, leading to a high production of glucocorticoids (mainly cortisol) resulting in somatovegetative syndromes. After the release of a large amount of tyreoliberin from the hypothalamus, the stimulation of the activity of the thyroid gland is reduced. This results in increased levels of tyreotropic hormones. This also causes somatovegetative syndromes to occur.

Corticoliberin also acts on the cornea of the adrenal gland, and catecholamines (adrenal norepinephrine) are produced in large quantities, causing somatovegetative syndromes. In general, during stress, the hormones adrenaline, Beta-endorphin, thyroxine, norepinephrine, cortisol, prolactin are produced:

Currently, stress is increasing in the world and becoming an urgent disease. This in turn is due to an increase in psychoemotional States. The fact that the above hormones are separated in large quantities during stress saabli they are called "stress hormones". Under the influence of Stress, a whole series of biochemical reactions begins, with which the body tries to protect itself, adapt to the stressful process. All stress hormones show decreased excitability, decreased

appetite, improved memory, increased attention-decreased induction, decreased euphoria, decreased sexual arousal TV'sir.

Stress during Stress determination of the concentration of hormones in the blood is somewhat easier in cortisol, prolactin, thyroxine, that is, the transfer of cortisol to an empty stomach from 8:00 to 9:30 in the morning is acquired by muxim ahamiyat. To detect prolactin, blood is administered on an empty stomach for 12 hours after 2soat after waking up. Thyroxine, on the other hand, should have at least 8th time between the last feeding and blood intake.

References:

1. Bilenko M. V. theoretical and experimental foundations of the use of antioxidant therapy to prevent acute ischemic injuries in organs // Bioantioxiifiers in the regulation of metabolism in the norm and pathology. M., 1982. Pp. 195-213.
2. Boldyrev A. A. oxidative stress and brain / / Soros training journal. 2001. No. 7. Pp. 21-27.
3. Lapin I. P. Neurochemical mosaic of individualization of anxiety and psychopharmacology / / anxiety and obsessions. Moscow: Rams publishing, 1998. Pp. 12-20.
4. Putilina M. V. possibilities of early drug correction of mental and autonomic disorders in hypertensive encephalopathy / / doctor. 2009. No. 9. Pp. 38-42.
5. Putilina M. V. neuroprotective therapy of chronic brain ischemia / / physician. 2008. No. 9. Pp. 34-38.
6. Smirnova I. N., Suslina Z. A., Tanashyan M. M. et al. Antioxidant and neurotrophic effects of cytoflavin in chronic cerebrovascular diseases // Bulletin of the St. Petersburg State Medical Academy. I. I. Mechnikov Academy. 2002. No. 3. Pp. 110-114.
9. Voronina T. A., Smirnov L. D., Goryainova I. I. mechanism of action and justification of the use of the drug Mexidol in neurology. M., 2000. p. 14.
11. Fedorova T. N. oxidative stress and protection of the brain from ischemic injury): dis. ... Doc. biol. nauk. M., 2004.12. Rickels K, Downing R, Schweizer E, Hassman H. Antidepressants for the treatment of generalized anxiety disorder. A placebo-controlled comparison of imipramine, trazodone, and diazepam. Arch Gen Psychiatry 1993; 50(11): 884-895;
13. Salomova, N. K. (2022). Risk factors for recurrent stroke. Polish journal of science N, 52, 33-35.
14. Qahharovna, S. N. (2023). Thromboocclusive Lesions of the Bronchocephalic Arteries: Treatment Options and Phytotherapy Options. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT, 2(2), 41-46.

15. Salomova Nilufar Kakhorovna//FEATURES OF NEUROREHABILITATION ITSELF DEPENDING ON THE PATHOGENETIC COURSE OF REPEATED STROKES, LOCALIZATION OF THE STROKE FOCUS AND THE STRUCTURE OF NEUROLOGICAL DEFICIT//European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability (EJRDS 11. 8-12. 2022/11
16. Salomova, N. K. (2022). Risk factors for recurrent stroke. Polish journal of science N, 52, 33-35.
17. Salomova, N. (2023). TRANSITOR ISCHEMIC ATTACK. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(7), 160-166.
18. Semaan W., Hergueta T., Bloch J., Charpak Y., Duburcq A., Le Guern M.E., Alquier C., Rouillon F., Cross-sectional study of the prevalence of adjustment disorder with anxiety in general practice.// Encephale. 2001. May-Jun. 27(3). P. 238-44;
19. Strine T.W., Chapman D.P., Kobau R. et al. Associations of self-reported anxiety symptoms with health-related quality of life and health behaviors.//Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol. 2005. Jun. 40(6). P. 432-8.
20. Seredenin S.B. Genetic differences on response to emotional stress and tranquilizers // Psychopharmacol & Biol. Narcol. 2003. V. 1-2. P. 494-509.
21. Marks I.E. Cure and care of neurosis. N.Y.: J.V. Scott Med. Found., 2001. 429 p.
22. Pollack M.H. Comorbid anxiety and depression // J. Clin. Psychiat. 2005. V. 66, suppl. 8. – P. 22-29.
23. Nutt D. Imaging receptors in human anxiety // Int. J. Neuropsychopharmacol. 2004. V. 7, suppl. 1. P. 17.
24. Redoux L. Neurotransmitter basis of anxiety // Anxiety: basic and clinical research. – N.Y.: Hammerworth Press, 2001. P. 36-50.

